

Multi-input convolutional neural network for breast cancer detection using thermal images and clinical data*

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Abstract

Background and objective: Breast cancer is the most common cancer in women. While mammography is the most widely used screening technique for the early detection of this disease, it has several disadvantages such as radiation exposure or high economic cost. Recently, multiple authors studied the ability of machine learning algorithms for early diagnosis of breast cancer using thermal images, showing that thermography can be considered as a complementary test to mammography, or even as a primary test under certain circumstances. Moreover, although some personal and clinical data are considered risk factors of breast cancer, none of these works considered that information jointly with thermal images.

Methods: We propose a novel approach for early detection of breast cancer combining thermal images of different views with personal and clinical data, building a multi-input classification model which exploits the benefits of convolutional neural networks for image analysis. First, we searched for structures using only thermal images. Next, we added the clinical data as a new branch of each of these structures, aiming to improve its performance.

Results: We applied our method to the most widely used public database of breast thermal images, the Database for Mastology Research with Infrared Image. The best model achieves a 97% accuracy and an area

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under the ROC curve of 0.99, with a specificity of 100% and a sensitivity of 83%.

Conclusions: After studying the impact of thermal images and personal and clinical data on multi-input convolutional neural networks for breast cancer diagnosis, we conclude that: (1) adding the lateral views to the front view improves the performance of the classification model, and (2) including personal and clinical data helps the model to recognize sick patients.

Keywords— Breast cancer; classification; clinical data; convolutional neural network; thermal images

1 Introduction

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), breast cancer is the most frequent cancer in women¹ and the second most common cancer in the world². Early detection of breast cancer is essential for finding the best treatment and reduce mortality³, being the development of screening protocols crucial to accomplish this goal. Most common methods used for cancer screening include clinical examination, mammography and ultrasound. Among them, mammography is considered as the gold standard for breast cancer screening [1].

Mammography has several important disadvantages. Its sensitivity is lower when facing high dense breasts or with younger woman (approximately below 45 years) [2]. The exposure to ionizing radiation increases the risk of developing breast cancer [3], which limits the mammography as a frequent screening modality. In order to get proper mammograms, breast region should be compressed, causing fear and pain to some women [1]. Its specificity is not very high [4], which leaves room for improvement to be considered, taking also into account that false positives carry psychological consequences on patients and increase medical costs [5]. Moreover, it is an expensive technique, so that some countries do not currently have the resources to carry out a screening program with periodic mammograms.

Thermography is a safe, low cost, non-invasive and non-contact cancer screening method that can detect tumors at an early stage, even in precancerous conditions [6]. The interpretation of the thermal images was carried out normally by human experts. Previous research indicated that the low diagnostic accuracy of thermograms was caused by weak technical ability and expertise in interpreting such images [6]. Fortunately, the advances in infrared cameras, the increase in the processing capacity of computers, the development and explosion of digital image processing and machine learning algorithms in the field of artificial intelligence, and the cheaper and easier access to GPU-based cloud computing resources have significantly improved in recent years the role of thermography as an effective and automatic tool for early breast abnormality detection [7]. Some studies suggest that thermography, when used with well-defined protocols, can detect early symptoms of cancer several years earlier than mammography [8, 6]. It can minimize diagnostic errors on women of any age and of any breast density, and it allows to implement periodic screening programs in countries with any level of resources. All these factors have led to studies that present

¹<https://www.who.int/cancer/prevention/diagnosis-screening/breast-cancer/en/>

²<https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/cancer>

³<https://www.who.int/cancer/detection/breastcancer/en/>

thermography as a good alternative to mammography or at least as a complementary test [9, 10, 7].

Several databases have been created in recent years to study the diagnostic ability of breast thermography, being those developed by the Proeng project⁴ and by the Department of Biotechnology-Tripura University-Jadavpur University (DBT-TU-JU) [11] the only public ones as far as we know. In this work, we use the Database for Mastology Research with Infrared Image (DMR) [12], developed by the Proeng project, which is the first thermography database created for early detection of breast cancer and the most widely used to date [6, 13].

DMR database contains thermal images from five different views of the breast: front, left oblique, right oblique, left lateral, and right lateral (we will give more details in Section 2.1). Numerous studies in the literature use this database for early diagnosis of breast cancer, some of them with promising results [7]. However, most of the studies we consulted only use the front views. Since breast cancer may also appear in the tail of the breast tissue, called tail of Spence, other views of breast may be useful for a proper diagnosis [14]. This way, some studies [14, 15] also use the left and right lateral views.

Several risk factors increase the probability of getting breast cancer [16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21]. According to [22], 20% of breast cancer patients have at least one risk factor, so it is important to take this information into account to estimate the relative risk of developing this disease. However, we have not found any work in the literature that uses the personal and clinical data available in the DMR database to make the diagnosis. We believe that such data together with imaging data can greatly improve diagnostic capacity. One should expect that adding relevant information to a classification model might improve (or at least not worsen) its performance.

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) [23] are a particular type of deep Neural Network (NN) that learn global patterns by using different types of neural layers. The ability of CNNs to automatically extract complex features from input data and the availability of software libraries that implement their functionality have made CNNs a very effective tool in recent years when applied to image processing [24]. However, it is striking that, despite their proven usefulness, CNNs have not been widely used in thermogram-based breast cancer detection [6].

The main objective of this work is to analyze whether adding the lateral images together with the patient’s personal and clinical data improve the diagnostic capacity of a model for early detection of breast cancer. To achieve this goal, we first built a diagnostic model based on multi-input CNNs [24, Chapter 7] that processes the front and lateral image views. Subsequently, from this model, we built a new model by adding as input the patient’s personal and clinical data. We measured and evaluated thoroughly the impact that each type of patient information has on the diagnostic capacity of the models.

This article is organized as follows. First, we outline the information structure of the database and explain how we cleansed and preprocessed the data. Next, we explain the methodology we have followed to design the experiments and models. Then, we present the results obtained. Finally, we analyze the results, comparing them with those in the literature.

⁴<http://visual.ic.uff.br/proeng/>

2 Methods

2.1 Data preparation

In our study, we used the DMR database⁵, aimed at early detection of breast cancer. The patients in the records of this database belong to the University Hospital Antônio Pedro (HUAP) of the Federal Fluminense University of Brazil. The database records thermal images, together with their thermal matrices (containing temperature information in each pixel), as well as personal and clinical data of 287 patients.

Thermal images were collected using a FLIR SC620 thermal camera according to well established *static* and *dynamic* protocols⁶ [12]. They have a resolution of 640×480 pixels and a thermal sensitivity of 40 mK. In the static protocol, the patient must remain seated on the bench for 10 minutes, supporting their arms, and leaving their armpits free. With this protocol, five thermal images are obtained for each patient, from five different views, namely, *front*, *right oblique* 45° (R45), *left oblique* 45° (L45), *right lateral* 90° (R90) and *left lateral* 90° (L90). The dynamic protocol produces 20 front sequential images (one every 15 seconds) and two lateral images (one R90 and one L90).

The personal and clinical data of each patient include the age, the diagnosis of breast cancer (healthy or sick), personal history (eating habits, last menstrual period, age at menarche, . . .), medical history (use of prostheses, use of hormone replacement, radiotherapy, . . .), and data on the application of the protocol (body temperature, if smoked or consumed alcohol two hours before, . . .).

As stated in [12], the acquisition and public use (under automatic registration) of this database was approved by the Ethical Committee of the HUAP and registered at the Brazilian Ministry of Health under number CAAE: 01042812.0.0000.5243.

2.2 Data cleansing

Data cleansing consists of identifying incomplete, incorrect, inaccurate, or irrelevant parts of the data in a record set or database, and then replacing, modifying, or deleting them. We applied data cleansing to the two parts of the database (images and personal and clinical data) and, finally, removed all the patients without thermal images or with severe inconsistencies in their personal and clinical data.

2.2.1 Thermal images cleansing

Given that several patients did not have all the thermal images of the static and dynamic protocols, in this work we have just taken three thermal images per patient, one of the front view, and one of each lateral view (L90 and R90). We consider that these three views are enough to cover all the breast region. When available, we take the thermal images from the static protocol because they have a similar body temperature. When not available, we take the thermal image from the dynamic protocol.

As the images were taken following well-defined static and dynamic protocols, they generally all have the same image quality. However, we found anomalies in a few patients, which led us to eliminate some thermal images. We removed images according to the following criteria:

⁵<http://visual.ic.uff.br/dmi/>

⁶<http://visual.ic.uff.br/dmi/prontuario/protocolo.pdf>

- Fuzzy images, where the shape of the breasts, and even the whole trunk of the body, is barely visible. The difference is very perceptible as can be seen in Figure 1.
- Images with some form of dressing in the breasts, which may cover any kind of injury and produce a thermal pattern similar to that of a tumor.
- Images that did not follow the established protocol, i.e., those in which patients had their arms down or were taken from different angles than they should.

Figure 1: Comparison between a fuzzy and a normal thermal image of the database.

When possible, we replaced the removed static views by the corresponding image in the dynamic protocol. In the case of L90 and R90 views, we took the only thermal image produced in this protocol. For the replacement of front views, we took the first front image of the dynamic sequence, since [25] reported that for many patients the first front image of the dynamic sequence was the same as the front image of the static protocol.

2.2.2 Personal and clinical data cleansing

Personal and clinical data in the DMR database presents several anomalies that must be addressed before analyzing these data.

We translated all the text (available in Portuguese, English and Spanish) into English and converted all the dates (available in six different formats) to the same format.

Homogenizing some features, such as the age at menarche and the age at menopause, required computing the real age of the patient at the time of the visit. As the current age of each patient is constantly updated in the database, we computed the age at the time of the patient’s visit, age_{visit} , as follows:

$$age_{visit} = age_{current} - (year_{current} - year_{visit}),$$

where $age_{current}$ is the age appearing in the patient records, $year_{current}$ is the current year and $year_{visit}$ is the year in which the visit is registered.

Some patients seem to have some information miss-swapped. These are the cases of the date of menarche (42 years old) and menopause (12 years old) of patient 267, and the age of last menstrual period (35 years old) and menopause (34 years old) of patient 261. We fixed both anomalies by swapping those dates.

We performed an analysis of all the free-text fields to extract relevant information. From these fields we were able to encode whether the patient had diabetes and whether she had history of family members with breast cancer, including the classification according to their degree of separation.

We finally removed all the patients with severe anomalies in their records, e.g., a patient who would be 113 at the time of the visit and registered her last menstrual period only a few months before.

After the data cleansing, we found that only 211 patients out of 287 have the front and both lateral (L90 and R90) views together with the personal and clinical data, having 170 patients labeled as *healthy* and 41 patients labeled as *sick*. Note the high imbalance of classes.

2.3 Data preprocessing

With respect to personal and clinical data, we selected and grouped the available features into three categories as follows.

- *Risk factors* include eating habits [16, 17], family history of cancer [17, 21], previous radiotherapy treatment [17], use of hormone replacement [17, 18], age [17, 21], age at menarche [16, 17, 20], age at menopause [16, 17, 20], diabetes [19] and presence of nodules [17].
- *Complementary features to the thermal images* include presence of prosthesis, signals of wart on breasts, changes in the nipples, and mastectomy. Although these features do not predict breast cancer on their own, they help interpret and analyze thermal images.
- *Protocol features* indicate if the patient smoked, drank coffee, consumed alcohol, did physical exercise, or put some pomade, deodorant or products at breasts or armpits region two hours before the visit. We assume that this information, as being part of the protocol, can explain differences in the body temperature.

Lastly, before feeding the network with these data, we applied min-max scaler to the selected personal and clinical features and to the thermal matrices, so that all the values lie in the interval $[0, 1]$. Normalization enhances the performance of the NNs, speeding up learning and accelerating their convergence.

2.4 Construction of the classification model

Once the data were cleansed and preprocessed, we created a classification model using the thermal images of the three views, measuring the impact of adding the lateral ones. After that, we added the personal and clinical data to the model and analyzed the effect of including such information on the predictive capacity of the model (the results are described in Section 3). Figure 2 shows the workflow of our proposed classification methods.

We defined our classification model as a multi-input CNN that takes as inputs the thermal images of the three views (front, R90 and L90), and outputs the probability of a patient being healthy or sick. Each input is first processed independently by a CNN branch (see Figure 3), and then the outputs of the three branches (namely CNN front, CNN R90, and CNN L90) are concatenated and processed together by a Final NN to obtain the global output.

Figure 2: Workflow of the proposed classification methods. The first one use only the thermal images, and the second one includes also the personal and clinical data.

CNNs consist mainly of three kinds of layers [23]: convolutional layers, whose role is to extract local features by means of a set of learnable filters; pooling layers, whose role is to reduce the size of output maps and extract dominant features; and dense or fully connected layers, whose role is to learn global patterns from a set of learnable parameters. Multi-input CNNs allow to combine input data from different sources, using different types of neural layers, and merging the extracted features to perform a global processing. This way, CNNs perform an automatic feature extraction from the images [26, 6].

Several characteristics of CNNs make them well suited to our problem. First, CNNs in recent years have proven to be quite effective for image-based diagnosis [27, 28, 29, 30]. Second, their multi-input capability allows to work alongside thermal images and personal and clinical data. Third, convolution and pooling layers automatically do a job of abstracting data from low-level features to higher-level features, where the deeper the layer, the more complex the extracted features. All these characteristics allow the model to minimize diagnostic errors.

After building the model as presented in Figure 3, we adapted its structure to include the 18 selected personal and clinical features of the patients. This way, we added a new branch where these data are processed by a NN. The outputs of this branch and the branches that process image views (CNN front, CNN R90, and CNN L90) are concatenated and processed jointly by a Final NN to obtain the global output. The workflow of this new model appears in Figure 4.

2.5 Evaluation framework

There is a common step in the design of both experiments: the data preparation and the choice of metrics to analyze the performance of the models and compare them with each other and with the ones appearing in the literature.

Recall that our dataset contains 211 patients, 170 of them labeled as *healthy* and 41 as *sick*. We randomly split the dataset into the three usual subsets, namely, train, validation and test, trying to preserve the proportion between both classes (*healthy* and *sick*) in each subset, as shown in Table 1. We also checked that the 18 selected features of the personal and clinical data appear homogeneously in the three subsets.

Table 1: Partition of data into train, validation and test sets

Subset	%	<i>healthy</i>	<i>sick</i>
train	70%	119	28
validation	15%	25	7
test	15%	26	6

We have used several metrics that are very common for evaluating classification models in a medical domain [31], and additionally, we used a metric called *weighted error*, described below:

- Accuracy. It is the proportion of instances correctly classified. It does not provide as useful information as the rest of the metrics due to the high imbalance of classes: the naive classification in which all the patients are classified as *healthy* already reaches an accuracy of 81.25% on the test set. However, since this metric

Figure 3: Structure of the classification model without personal and clinical data.

Figure 4: Structure of the classification model with personal and clinical data. Nodes in green reuse the structure and hyperparameters obtained in the model in Figure 3.

is the one that is mainly used in the literature, we keep it in order to compare our results with those in the literature.

- Area under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve (AUC ROC). It measures how much the model is capable of distinguishing between classes; it usually takes values between 0.5 and 1. In medical context, it quantifies the diagnostic performance of the model, where values closer to 1 mean good test results and values closer to 0.5, bad test results.
- False Positives (FP). It measures how many records with label *healthy* are incorrectly classified as *sick* by the model.
- False Negatives (FN). It measures how many records with label *sick* are incorrectly classified as *healthy* by the model.
- Sensitivity. It is the quotient between the number of patients correctly classified as sick and the actual number of sick patients in the set.
- Specificity. It is the quotient between the number of patients correctly classified as healthy and the actual number of healthy patients in the set.
- Weighted Error (WE). This is a metric introduced in [32]. It is defined as follows:

$$WE = FP + rate \cdot FN, \quad (1)$$

where $rate > 0$ is the relative cost of a false negative versus a false positive. Given two classification models, if neither of them is better than the other in the FP and in the FN, then the WE allows to compare them based on the fact that a false positive, while it may cause anxiety and discomfort to the patient and lead to an unnecessary biopsy (with the economic cost that this implies) [4], is not as serious as a false negative [33], as it may delay the cancer detection, which could involve more expensive and aggressive treatments, and dramatically reduce the survival rate [34]. After consulting with some specialists, we take $rate = 20$. As we know that this is a subjective value, we will discuss it in Section 4.

Even though some of these metrics may seem redundant, we have computed all for clarity and to facilitate the interpretation of the results when comparing the models.

Finally, given the high imbalance of classes (see Table 1), we have used the following class weights to train the models: 1 for *healthy* and $119/28 = 4.25$ for *sick*.

2.5.1 Classification model with front and lateral views

As explained in Section 2.4, we have defined our classification model as a multi-input CNN that takes as inputs the thermal images and outputs the probability of a patient being healthy or sick. In order to find a good model for the data, we evaluated several structures for the three branches (CNN front, CNN R90, CNN L90), and the Final NN, taking in turn different sets of hyperparameters for each structure. We combined train and validation sets in one set and performed a 5-fold cross-validation in all the defined structures, using the results to refine the model structure and hyperparameters. Finally, we kept the best model obtained in the cross-validation step.

2.5.2 Classification model with front and lateral views and personal and clinical data

The next step of our research is to add the 18 selected personal and clinical features of the patients (described in Section 2.3) to the classification model and analyze their

impact in the performance of the model. Since we found no works in the literature to compare with, we decided to build different models to measure the effect of adding that information in different model structures.

To build these models, we first designed their structures using the thermal images following the process described in Section 2.5.1, being the model obtained in that section one of them.

After we determined the best structure and hyperparameters for each model without clinical data, we added a new branch with the personal and clinical data (NN data, see Figure 4). We optimized the structure and hyperparameters of this branch, keeping the rest of the network fixed. Since personal and clinical data require different processing than images, this branch has a different structure.

By following this process we obtained 14 different models (seven with personal and clinical data and seven without it). We evaluated them on the corresponding test sets and compared the results obtained from the models with personal and clinical data versus the ones obtained without personal and clinical data to analyze the effect of including that information. These results are presented in Section 3.

3 Results

3.1 Classification model with front and lateral views

Following the process described in Section 2.5.1 we obtain a model in which, according to the notation used in Figure 3, CNN R90 and CNN L90 have the same structure and hyperparameters, while CNN front has different structure and hyperparameters. Each of these CNNs consists of a convolutional part and a fully connected part.

The convolutional part of CNN front consists of three blocks of convolutional layers and a max pooling layer. In the first block there are two convolutional layers, with 32 and 64 filters, respectively; in the second block there are three convolutional layers, with 64 filters each; in the third block there are four convolutional layers, with 128 filters each.

The convolutional part of CNN L90 (and CNN R90) also consists of three blocks of convolutional layers and a max pooling layer. In the first block there are two convolutional layers, with 32 filters each; in the second block there are three convolutional layers, with 64 filters each; in the third block there are three convolutional layers, with 128 filters each.

Each convolutional part is connected with its respective fully connected part through a flatten layer. The structure and hyperparameters of the three fully connected parts are the same. Each of them consists of two blocks, each containing a dense layer (with 512 neurons in the first block and 128 in the second block), a batch normalization layer and a dropout layer with rate of 0.5 in both cases. These two blocks are followed by two dense layers, the first one with 64 neurons and the last one with one neuron, representing the probability that the patient is sick, based on each view.

The outputs of the three branches are concatenated and processed together through a final dense layer with one neuron, which outputs the final probability. The model was trained using stochastic gradient descent.

3.2 Results of the classification model with front and lateral views

Our model achieves a classification accuracy of 97% on the test set, misclassifying only one patient. Moreover, AUC ROC reached is 0.99, meaning a great diagnostic performance of the model, which is summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Results on the test set of the classification model for the front and lateral views.

Acc. (%)	AUC ROC	FP	FN	Sens. (%)	Spec. (%)	WE
97	0.99	0	1	83	100	20

3.3 Results of the classification models with personal and clinical data

Table 3 shows the results on the test sets of the seven models with and without personal and clinical data. Notice that M. 4 without personal and clinical data (“M.4 ncd” in the table) is the model whose results are shown in Section 3.2.

After evaluating the seven pairs of models (with and without personal and clinical data) in the corresponding test sets, we obtained that the accuracy increases in five of them after adding the personal and clinical data. AUC ROC increases in four models, and decreases in the other three, being the decrease negligible in two of them.

The specificity increases in five models when adding the personal and clinical data, and the sensitivity increases in two models and remains the same for the other five. The sensitivity reaches 100% in five of the seven models.

In five of the models, both the FP and the FN are reduced or maintained when using personal and clinical data, while in models M. 1 and M. 4 one of these two metrics decreases, while the other increases. We have studied these two cases using the WE, finding that in both of them it is lower for the model with personal and clinical. The mean and the standard deviation of the metrics for the seven models is always better with personal and clinical data than without it, except for the standard deviation of the WE.

4 Discussion

As far as we know, this is the first work that builds a model for breast cancer detection with a multi-input CNN using thermal images from different views. The results appearing in Table 2 illustrate that the model has a great diagnostic performance, classifying and distinguishing between healthy and sick patients.

The model, described in Section 3.1, is an ensemble in which the CNN branches calculate a set of local probabilities that are concatenated and processed by a NN that outputs a global prediction [24, Chapter 7]. In this way, each branch classifies a different thermal image view. We also tested other kind of structures, in which the inner networks only had convolutional and max pooling layers or the fully connected part was deeper or more shallow.

Table 3: Results on the test sets of the seven models.

Model	Acc. (%)	AUC ROC	FP	FN	Sens. (%)	Spec. (%)	WE
M. 1 ncd	87	0.82	2	2	67	92	42
M. 1 cd	81	0.89	6	0	100	77	6
M. 2 ncd	75	0.90	8	0	100	69	8
M. 2 cd	78	0.91	7	0	100	73	7
M. 3 ncd	78	0.92	7	0	100	73	7
M. 3 cd	84	0.90	5	0	100	81	5
M. 4 ncd	97	0.99	0	1	83	100	20
M. 4 cd	91	0.98	3	0	100	88	3
M. 5 ncd	81	0.87	4	2	67	85	44
M. 5 cd	84	0.91	3	2	67	88	43
M. 6 ncd	75	0.92	8	0	100	69	8
M. 6 cd	81	0.95	6	0	100	77	6
M. 7 ncd	87	0.92	2	2	67	92	42
M. 7 cd	94	0.87	0	2	67	100	40
Mean ncd	83	0.91	4.43	1.00	83	83	24.43
Mean cd	85	0.92	4.28	0.57	91	83	15.71
Std ncd	8.01	0.05	3.26	1.00	16.50	12.56	17.62
Std cd	5.76	0.04	2.43	0.98	16.10	9.25	17.68

ncd stands for “no personal and clinical data” and *cd* stands for “personal and clinical data”. *Std* stands for standard deviation.

The fact that CNN R90 and CNN L90 have the same structure and hyperparameters is reasonable since an R90 view can be understood as a vertical flip of a L90 view and vice versa (which corresponds to a common type of data augmentation). Therefore, one would expect that if a model fits one of these two views, it would fit the other as well. Nevertheless, we tested models with different structures or hyperparameters for both sets of lateral images, obtaining worse results.

It seems reasonable to assume that the front views should be processed differently than the lateral ones, since they contain more information, as they capture both breasts (numerous studies obtain good classification results only with front images). We tested a model with the same structure and hyperparameters as CNN L90 and CNN R90 using as inputs front images, obtaining bad results, thus reinforcing the idea that CNN front should be different from CNN L90 (and, consequently, from CNN R90).

We compared our results with articles that used the DMR database for classification purposes. As we mentioned in Section 1, we only found two works in the literature [14, 15] that use both front and lateral thermal images. The approaches followed in these works are different from ours. They feed the classification models with manu-

ally defined features extracted from previously segmented thermal images, instead of following an end-to-end approach, feeding the model directly with the thermal images.

Table 4: Comparison of our model with those of the literature with both front and lateral views.

Article	Acc. (%)	AUC ROC	Sens. (%)	Spec. (%)
Ours	97	0.99	83	100
[14]	99 ↑	0.98	100 ↑	98
[15]	96	0.96	100 ↑	92

Up arrow means that the result is better than ours.

As shown in Table 4, our model obtains higher AUC ROC, which implies that it has learned to better distinguish between healthy and sick patients. Our model reaches a lower sensitivity but a higher specificity.

When assessing the excellent results obtained in [14], we should note that it seems they have evaluated their model using the complete database rather than just the test set (consisting of patients that the model has never seen before). It would be interesting to study the ability of their model to generalize (react to new data).

Next, we compare the performance of our model with those that only consider the front views. Table 5 contains the results of these models (for those articles which construct several models, we just included the results of the best one).

Table 5: Comparison of our model with those of the literature which use only front views.

Article	Acc. (%)	AUC ROC	Sens. (%)	Spec. (%)
Ours	97	0.99	83	100
[35]	85	–	87 ↑	83
[36]	90	0.95	95 ↑	85
[37]	89	0.93	86 ↑	100
[38]	88	–	80	93
[39]	90	–	87 ↑	93
[40]	98 ↑	–	–	–
[41]	98 ↑	–	98 ↑	98
[42]	91	–	93 ↑	90
[43]	98 ↑	0.98	94 ↑	100
[44]	89	0.92	86 ↑	90
[45]	88	0.92	87 ↑	89
[46]	91	–	87 ↑	94

Up arrow means that the result is better than ours.

All these articles but [40] perform a manual feature extraction prior to classification. In [40], they use CNNs to perform automatic classification, without segmenting the thermal images, just like we did. It is important to note the difference between

these two approaches. The first one defines in advance a set of “known” relevant thermal features and extracts them from the thermal matrices [47, 31, 48], feeding a model (for example a NN) with them. The second approach delegates this task to the CNN itself, which uses convolution and pooling layers to learn and extract the features that allow the best classification directly from the inputs (the thermal matrices). Some of the papers also perform image segmentation. Our model outperforms most of those in the literature, in particular, it achieves the highest AUC ROC and specificity, and our accuracy is quite similar to the best one.

Although none of the models in the literature have 100% sensitivity (they have false negatives in their classification), we would have expected a better sensitivity result in our model than the one obtained. As we mention before, our model only misclassified one sick patient but, given the low number of sick patients in the test set, this mistake is highly penalized by this metric. It would be interesting to know the number of false negatives and false positives of these works in order to develop a more detailed comparison.

We would like to highlight that models in [41, 43] achieve good results. Concerning [41], the split of the dataset is not specified. Regarding [43], as in [14], the authors evaluated the model with the complete dataset (instead of just the test set). These facts make difficult to compare their results with ours and to know how these models would react to new data.

An essential difference of our study with most of the literature is that we do not perform image segmentation or manual feature extraction (as said, before CNNs perform automatic feature extraction from images). One should expect that segmenting the images would improve the model performance as it would help to locate the breasts. However, our study shows that by using the front and lateral thermal images, and then adding the personal and clinical data, we achieve similar or even better results, avoiding the segmentation and manual feature extraction steps.

Table 3 shows that personal and clinical data helps to better detect sick cases, reducing the FN and, therefore, improving the sensitivity of the model. Moreover, since AUC ROC increases in four of the seven models, and in two of them it stays pretty the same, we may suppose that personal and clinical data helps the model to better distinguish between healthy and sick patients. According to that table, the best performing model with personal and clinical data is M. 4. Comparing the results obtained with this model with those in Table 5 we observe that, even though the accuracy has been reduced, it is still very good, being only surpassed by three of the 12 models, and it achieves the highest AUC ROC and sensitivity. In exchange, the specificity has been reduced.

Computing the WE, see Equation (1), requires assigning a value to *rate*, but we have not found any reference in the literature to know precisely which value to take. However, some studies [33, 49] indicate that the negative consequences of a false negative are greater than of a false positive, thus suggesting that it is reasonable to assume that *rate* should be greater than 1. On the recommendation of experts we take a *rate* of 20. Looking at the results of the FP and the FN presented in Table 3, we can conclude that in five of the seven models the value of *rate* would not have affected the results of comparing the model with personal and clinical data versus without personal and clinical data, i.e., in these cases adding personal and clinical data always helps to detect breast cancer. Only in M. 1, when $rate \leq 2$, and in M. 4, when $rate \leq 3$ (see Fig. 5), adding personal and clinical data would worsen the performance of the model. But in both models, the *rate* is far lower than the one proposed by the experts.

Finally, we would like to point out some limitations of the DMR database. Its

Figure 5: WE in M. 4 for different values of *rate*.

small size (only 287 patients before data cleansing) makes it difficult to apply deep learning techniques. Another important detail is the lack of homogeneity in personal and clinical data and that a lot of information is written in free text, which must be analyzed. Nevertheless, we would like to value this database, since, as far as we know, it is the only public database with thermal images for breast cancer detection, collecting a lot of relevant information from patients.

5 Conclusions and future work

To our knowledge, this work is the first to use a multi-input CNN for early detection of breast cancer using thermal images from different views and personal and clinical data. The main conclusions of the study are:

- i. A classification model that considers the front and lateral views is able to distinguish between healthy and sick patients very accurately.
- ii. Personal and clinical data allows classification models to better detect sick patients, thus improving their diagnostic performance.

These conclusions agree with the assumption we made at the beginning of the work: adding quality information might improve the classification capacity of the model.

Our work shows that the image segmentation carried out by most of the articles could be avoided by taking more information of each patient. We get similar or better results just by using the lateral views and some personal and clinical features. This greatly simplifies image processing when the objective is solely to classify and not to locate.

Although relevant information is not always available, mainly in public databases, including more information is essential to build models which provide reliable diagnosis, especially in a medical domain.

Regarding future lines of work, it would be interesting to perform image segmentation and to compare the results with the ones obtained in this study. Although in our approach CNNs extract features automatically, it would also be interesting to compare this approach with the one that extracts manually-defined relevant features from the thermal images, and uses these features to feed a classification model.

Finally, we chose to include personal and clinical data as inputs of a NN. Although this approach has given good results, it would also be interesting to use other classification algorithms that may allow explainability, and combine their predictions with that of the CNN for the images.

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